

Measurement Report

Sample Name : 1

Measurement Date: 26.08.2025 12:20

by: ExpertName

Report Date: 26.08.2025 12:27

by: ExpertName

SOP : DefaultSOP

Solvent : Water

Refractive index : 1.331

Viscosity at 24.99 °C : 0.889 cP

Device : Amerigo

Wavelength : 638 nm

Laser power : 10 %

Temperature set by: None

Resolution : MEDIUM

Dielectric Constant: 78.06

Electrode Distance : 5 mm

Henry function : Smoluchowski

Experiment : Acquisition

Measurements per sequence: 6

Overview

Start Time (hh:mm:ss)	Carrier frequency(Hz)	Resistivity factor (V)	Applied field (V/cm)	Laser Power (%)
8/26/2025 12:20:31 PM	8001	5.631	20.3	10

	Mean	Std Dev
Mobility (µm.cm / V.s)	-3.12	0.14
Zeta Potential (mV)	-40.17	1.86

Measurement n°	Mobility (µm.cm / V.s)	Zeta (mV)
1	-3.41	-43.82
2	-3.03	-38.95
3	-3.22	-41.39
4	-3.03	-38.95
5	-3.03	-38.95
6	-3.03	-38.95

Start (hh:mm:ss) : 26.08.2025 12:20
T(°C) : 25°C Applied field (V/cm) : 20.3
Reference intensity (kcps) 108
Scattering intensity (kcps) 2538